

Innovative concepts and technologies for ecologically sustainable nutrient management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

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DELIVERABLE 1.1

PLAN FOR THE DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION

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Deliverable lead	CETRI
Authors	Ioanna Thomatou (CETRI)
Reviewers	Dimitris Savvas (AUA), Dora Lola
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Partners short names

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country
1	COO	AUA	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON	EL
2	BEN	UAL	UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA	ES
3	BEN	UTH	PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS	EL
4	BEN	IGZ	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR GEMUSE- UND ZIERPFLANZENBAU GROSSBEEREN/ERFURTEV	DE
5	BEN	CETRI	CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (CETRI) LTD	CY
6	BEN	WUR	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	NL
7	BEN	NIBIO	NIBIO - NORSK INSTITUTT FOR BIOKONOMI	NO
8	BEN	ARI	MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE, RURAL DEVELOPMENT AND ENVIRONMENT OF CYPRUS	CY
9	BEN	ESSRG	ESSRG NONPROFIT KFT	HU
10	BEN	UNITO	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO	IT
11	BEN	UTAD	UNIVERSIDADE DE TRAS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO	PT
12	BEN	COEXPHAL	ASOCIACION DE ORGANIZACIONES DE PRODUCTORES DE FRUTAS Y HORTALIZAS DE ALMERIA	ES
13	BEN	METEC	METEC INNOVATION CONSULTING SRL	IT
14	BEN	ODYC	ODYC	BE
15	BEN	Vervaet	FRANS VERVAET B.V.	NL
16	BEN	ATB	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR AGRARTECHNIK UND BIOKONOMIE EV	DE
17	BEN	WP	WONDERPLANT THERMOKIPIA ANONYMI ETAIRIA	EL
18	BEN	InHort	INSTYTUT OGRODNICTWA - PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	PL
19	BEN	Augmenta	AUGMENTA AGRICULTURE TECHNOLOGIES MONOPROSOPI IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKIETAIREIA	EL
20	BEN	LGNL	LTO GLASKRACHT NEDERLAND (LGNL)	NL
21	BEN	EV ILVO	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	BE
22	BEN	SPI	SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACAO CONSULTADORA EMPRESARIAL E FOMENTODA INOVACAO SA	PT
23	AP	HAAS	Institute of Soil Fertilizer and Environmental Resources, Heilongjiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences	CN

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country
24	AP	Stanley	Stanley Agriculture Group	CN
25	AP	SVG	Shouguang Vegetable Industry Holding Group Co.,Ltd	CN
26	AP	NAU	Nanjing Agricultural University	CN
27	AP	CAU	CHINA AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY	CN
28	AP	HAAFS	Institute of Agro-resources and Environment, hebeiAcademy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences	CN
29	AP	CG	CLEANGROW UK LIMITED	UK
30	AP	JHI	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	UK

Abbreviations

PDEC	Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
P1	During the project and 1 year after its end
DoA	Description of Action
P2	The next 5 years
SHG	Stakeholder Group
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The **ECONUTRI Deliverable 1.1**, the first version of the “Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication” (PDEC), outlines the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (D&E&C) activities to be undertaken by the consortium as part of WP1. This plan aims to maximize the impact of the project and will include an analysis of target groups and proposed channels for interacting with stakeholders. Additionally, the plan will detail communication measures for promoting the project and its outcomes, policy feedback measures to contribute to policy shaping, and a follow-up plan to foster the exploitation and uptake of all results.

All partners are committed to actively participate in dissemination, communication, and exploitation actions under the coordination of the WP1 leader CETRI. The D&E&C activities in China will be coordinated by SPI, which possesses offices and a robust network in China, with the full engagement of all Chinese partners.

All partners in the consortium will implement awareness campaigns in their respective countries and networks, contribute news and updates to the web portal and newsletter, and help keep the project's social media accounts active. The partners will also translate any material required in their local languages to amplify the impact of ECONUTRI. The WP1 leader (CETRI) is responsible for developing all the communication tools, with the aim of raising visibility and awareness of the project and its objectives.

This deliverable outlines the dissemination and communication strategy of the ECONUTRI consortium and aims to serve as a strategic document which partners will refer to, in order to implement successfully their individual and joint D&E&C activities. We outline the dissemination activities that have taken place so far, along with some potential future events we have planned. In addition, we provide an initial dissemination plan which combines individual exploitation perspectives of each partner as well as the overall project's anticipated impact.

The ECONUTRI project is still in its initial phase at M6, and many aspects of the PDEC are still being developed and refined. As such, the PDEC will be consistently reviewed and updated to ensure it aligns with the project's goals and effectively supports its objectives.

Two additional versions of the project are planned: a second version in the middle of the project at M18, and a third and final version at the end of the project at M42.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF TABLES.....	6
LIST OF FIGURES.....	6
1 INTRODUCTION.....	7
2 OBJECTIVES OF DELIVERABLE	7
3 DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION STRATEGY.....	8
4 TARGET AUDIENCE AND KEY MESSAGES.....	8
5 DISSEMINATION PLAN	10
5.1 Dissemination Actions up to month 6.....	11
5.2 Dissemination Actions in the future.....	13
5.2.1 Events planned for the years 2023/2024.....	13
5.2.2 Stakeholder engagement events	17
5.2.3 Clustering activities & EU-China Cooperation https://china.enrichcentres.eu/	17
6 COMMUNICATION PLAN.....	18
6.1 Visual Identity.....	18
6.1.1 ECONUTRI Logo.....	18
6.1.2 ECONUTRI colours.....	19
6.1.3 ECONUTRI Templates.....	19
6.2 Website	20
6.3 Leaflet.....	20
6.4 Roll up banner	21
6.5 Social media	22
6.6 Communication actions in the future	23
7 EXPLOITATION PLAN	25
7.1 Partner specific exploitation Plans.....	27
8 CONCLUSION.....	29
ANNEX 1	30

ANNEX 2	30
ANNEX 3	31

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 - Target Groups	9
Table 2 - Dissemination Tools.....	10
Table 3 - Events Planned (M6-18)	13
Table 4 – ECONUTRI Website structure	20
Table 5 - ECONUTRI Social media profiles.....	23
Table 6 – Communication tools.....	24
Table 8 - ECONUTRI Key Exploitable Results and expected TRLs	26
Table 9 - Partner Primary Exploitation plan	27

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 - ECONUTRI logo	18
Figure 2 - EU logo	18
Figure 3 - ECONUTRI logo colours	19
Figure 4 - ECONUTRI 3-fold leaflet	21
Figure 5 - ECONUTRI rollup banner	22

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of ECONUTRI is to optimize and validate at commercial level nutrient management technologies that minimize or even eliminate nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) pollution by limiting N emissions to soil, water and air and P emissions to water resources which can harm the environment when they leach into the soil and water or evaporate into the air.

ECONUTRI aims to use nature-based solutions to reduce pollution of water, soil and air by nutrient emissions originating from agriculture, including greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, the project will train farmers and scientists on the innovative technologies validated and demonstrated by the consortium so they can be used to improve soil, water, and air quality in Europe and China, and contribute in mitigation of global climate change.

The PDEC deliverable is a critical component of ECONUTRI's overall goal, as it aims to raise awareness of the project, to share, promote and utilize project results by relevant stakeholders and ultimately, maximize the impact of the project outcomes in EU, associated countries and China. The main goal is to define a common strategy for the consortium to structure an effective communication and dissemination action plan, highlighting the project's results and maximizing the impact of ECONUTRI.

The main aims of the Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication are:

1. Widely disseminate the project results to audiences that are expected to use the results in their own work
2. Plan how the partners will exploit / use the project results and manage intellectual property rights (IPR)
3. Communicate the project and its results to multiple audiences beyond the project's own community.

The dissemination and communication plan has been developed by CETRI with the active involvement of all partners. The dissemination and communication plan of ECONUTRI has been set up by M6 of the project as a valuable resource that **partners can use as a reference point/guidance** for implementing their various D&E&C activities. The plan will be updated throughout the project's runtime according to the needs and requirements that may arise. Additionally, this plan will be used as the main input for drafting release 2 and 3 of the PDEC as described in the DoA.

2 OBJECTIVES OF DELIVERABLE

The main objective of the ECONUTRI Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy is to promote the project's innovation character and to maximize its impact by widely spreading its outcomes to stakeholders and the public using the appropriate tools and methods for each stakeholder and target group.

Thus, the PDEC outlines a strategy to effectively communicate the project's goals and achievements, providing partners with guidance on how to plan and execute their dissemination activities. The PDEC is a dynamic document that will be adjusted and updated as the project progresses and new actions may be required.

Moreover, the PDEC aims to assist partners in designing, planning, and implementing their communication activities. For each communication approach, there are specific monitoring tools and materials provided to all partners in the consortium by CETRI.

The project community will continuously support dissemination efforts to facilitate exploitation of all results. A high project visibility and active stakeholder interaction are essential to build project awareness, maximize exploitation potential, and promote accountability that justifies the use of public funds to support this Innovation Action project.

Early dissemination planning increases impact and collaboration opportunities, and guarantees the project's greatest impact on stakeholders outside of the consortium. This ensures that project outputs are fully exploited, knowledge is made available to interested organizations, elements of excellence are reused, decision-makers are informed, and societal benefits are highlighted.

3 DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

Dissemination and communication activities will be complementary and synergistic, targeting a wide range of stakeholders. Partners will **disseminate the project results** to audiences that are expected to use the results in their own work, including scientific community in nutrient management, farmers, companies in the agro-food sector, policymakers, authorities. They will also **communicate the project and its results** to multiple audiences beyond the project's own community including investors, media and the public.

Collectively, the approach will inform and reach out to society, highlighting the importance of applying advanced nutrient management strategies in agriculture. All dissemination and communication activities will be precisely targeted and tailored to each group of intended project stakeholders and will continue after the project's end. This will be achieved by scaling up the application of the 24 innovative technologies deployed by ECONUTRI, based on the exploitation plans of the respective partners (see Section 7.1), which are currently being worked out in more detail.

4 TARGET AUDIENCE AND KEY MESSAGES

When developing a plan for dissemination and communication, it is important to identify who the target audience is. This may be a diverse range of audiences potentially interested in the ECONUTRI goals and outcomes. Once the target audience is identified, the best methods and channels can be determined for communication and dissemination activities.

The target audience also plays a crucial role in evaluating the PDEC's effectiveness. By monitoring how well the message is being received by the target audience, adjustments can be made to the PDEC to ensure that it is effectively reaching and engaging with them. This ongoing evaluation allows for a more targeted and effective communication strategy that can better meet the needs of the intended audience.

Once the target audience has been identified, the next crucial step is to create messages that are tailored to them. Effective communication requires messages that are relevant and aligned with the project's objectives, and that engage the identified groups of interest to maximize impact. These messages will undergo refinement as the project progresses and will align with specific materials and promotional activities. It is important to maintain a friendly, straightforward, and fact-based tone to ensure that the messages are easily understood by the target audience.

To this end, key messages that highlight the benefits of ECONUTRI are presented below in Table 1 and are linked to certain target groups. The tools and channels required for the messages to reach the target audience are also identified in Table 1 which is taken directly from the proposal. As we move forward, the wording and tone of these messages will be adjusted to suit the intended target group, the dissemination actions (publications, articles, events) and the communication tools (leaflets, presentations, social media posts).

Table 1 - Target Groups

Targeted groups in EU & China	How to reach them	Key message
Farming Industry (FI): Farmers, farming associations, cooperatives, Chambers of Agriculture, agribusiness professionals, advisors.	Exhibitions, fairs, workshops, media.	Reduce fertilizers cost, grow healthier products, contribute to pollution reduction, protect your own health.
Agro-food Companies (AC): ICT/nutrient management / precision agriculture / IOT / smart farming companies, traders, technology providers.	B2B meetings, invitation at project events and workshops, online and face to face meetings, social media.	Substantial profits for investing in a new generation of agricultural innovations. Access a new network of farming stakeholders in EU and China,
Authorities (A): local, regional, Ministries (agriculture, economy, environment), standardization and certification bodies, statistical offices.	F2F meetings, invitation to project events / workshops.	Creation of opportunities for growth, environment protection, new jobs, citizen-centered products.
Policy Makers (PM): experts on regulatory/policy issues related to Nutrients management, environmental organisations, NGOs.	Online and face to face meetings, invitation to project events & workshops.	ECONUTRI will incorporate innovations in nutrient management implementing relevant directives.
Scientific Community (SC): Leading researchers in the key areas of nutrients management, smart farming, IoT. Research Centers and Universities.	Publications, articles, conferences, workshops, research networks, clustering	All data created /collected during the project, not bound to IPR constraints, will be available on open royalty-free basis
Research Projects (RP): Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020, PRIMA, LIFE+, other EU or Chinese funding streams on addressing agricultural pollution issues.	Clustering activities, common workshops.	Let's partner up to maximize our combined impact on clean environment and reach as many stakeholders as possible.
Investors (I): Funding bodies, private equity firms, venture capital investors, innovation brokers	B2B meetings, invitation to project events & workshops.	High ROI by investing in the ECONUTRI technologies and innovations
Media (M): Websites, portals, popular You Tubers, journalists, internet, social media influencers, local TV stations	Targeted articles, videos, infographics, advertisements.	Learn about our EU funded project promoting reduction of pollution from agriculture.
General public(GP): citizens, individuals interested in climate change and environmental issues.	Social media, public events, publications videos, website.	Learn about the European-Chinese effort to reduce pollution from intensive agriculture.

5 DISSEMINATION PLAN

It is important to choose the dissemination activities that carry the greatest potential to achieve the ECONUTRI objectives and reach out to the right audience. The project team has strong representation across disciplines with important contacts in leading scientific and industrial networks in EU and China, allowing direct collaboration with these groups. Several key important dissemination materials, tools, and activities have been selected in the ECONUTRI project and are outlined below in Table 2. However, it's worth noting that this list below is a live document and will be continuously updated throughout the project.

Table 2- Dissemination Tools

Dissemination tool	Performance indicators		
	P1	P2	Means of verification
Publications in high Impact Factor journals or international scientific conferences on nutrients management, smart farming, climate change and IOT.	at least 20 peer-reviewed articles	>20 peer-reviewed articles	List of publications
Official EU Key Tools as the Horizon Results Platform, Horizon Dashboard, CORDIS, and theInnovation Radar (IR), EU magazines as Euronews, Horizon Magazine, Project Stories, research*eu results magazine.	Use of all Key Tools. 5 articles published at EU magazines	6 popular articles published at EU magazines	Project reporting
Articles published in smart farming and environmental magazines.	at least 5 articles	at least 5 articles	Project reporting
ECONUTRI Innovation handbook (publicly available and free to download) presenting lessons learnt during the project, suggesting best practices & providing policy recommendations.	>1000 views /downloads	3500 new downloads	Website analytics

During the first 6 months of the project more dissemination activities have been discussed and have been actively supported by all partners. Below we describe some of these activities that have been incorporated in the PDEC plan:

- **Presentations in conferences:** Presenting research results at relevant conferences with high-quality content and visual aids such as graphs, charts, and infographics can have a significant impact, enhancing visibility and recognition of the work.
- **Organization of Events:** To effectively convey a strong message and ensure that the audience comprehends it well, events with face-to-face discussions have a much stronger impact. Such events enable the establishment of long-term relationships and provide valuable insights from target stakeholders. Despite having a relatively small audience the connections made are powerful and enduring. Moreover, events of this nature offer excellent content for communication channels. Coupling such an event with a larger one, such as a conference or fair, can further amplify its impact. Whether held in-person or online, each type of event offers unique advantages. Combining both can prove to be a highly effective strategy. One such activity is the organization of a **Stakeholder Conference** as a satellite event to the I International Symposium on Protected Cultivation, Nettings and Screens for Mild Climates, which is organised by the ISHS and the Agricultural University of Athens in Athens on 23 to 26 September 2024.
- **Networking with other projects:** There are some other projects in the field with similar objectives, developing similar knowledge. Examples are the sister project '[trans4num](#)' that was approved under the same call, and the '[PestNu](#)' (H2020) project. ECONUTRI aims at developing clustering activities and other forms of collaboration with these projects. Although much of the work involved may be

confidential, there are still common activities that can be organized, such as public workshops or conferences. Collaborating in a collective effort, can lead to a more significant impact and added value to the EC, than working independently, especially in terms of achieving scientific excellence, improving competitiveness, and addressing societal challenges. And thus, demonstrating the long-term benefits of the EU funding to research, innovation and policy formation.

- Patents:** Patenting a process or technology is a significant achievement in research. It demonstrates that the research stands out from others, has exceptional quality and a strong potential for the market. Patents serve as a critical factor in ensuring the continuity of the project and its potential for producing concrete economic and scientific outcomes. ECONUTRI aims to implement 24 innovative technologies that can effectively combat nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) pollution, and keep N/P emissions within ecologically safe limits at the European, regional, and local levels. These cutting-edge technologies have a high potential for patent formation.

5.1 Dissemination Actions up to month 6

Since the start of ECONUTRI the following dissemination actions have been undertaken by the partners, tailored to the specific target groups for each activity:

1. AUA (P1)

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
Made a press release in a Greek radio station in Ierapetra, Crete spreading the ECONUTRI voice in Crete, a high stakeholder regional area full of greenhouses	Crete TV station listeners, general public of Crete Farming Industry in Crete, Agrofood companies in Crete., Greek Authorities,
Conference organizations: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> "New technologies aiming to reduce water and nutrient requirements in greenhouse crops" in Preveza, Greece on 16 Jan. 2023, "Sustainable fertilisation of Greenhouse vegetables" in Marathon, Attica on 12 Feb. 2023 "New Technologies to reduce consumption of water and fertilizers in greenhouse crops" in Crete, Greece on 17 March 2023. 	Farming Industry, Agrofood companies, Scientific community, Investors
AUA attended the kick-off meeting of the sister project "Trans4num" at the University of Hohenheim in Stuttgart on 22 Feb. 2023. In this meeting the Coordinators of ECONUTRI and Trans4num discussed opportunities for networking and clustering events as key strategies for enhancing collaboration and knowledge-sharing among similar projects.	Scientific Community-Clustering activities
AUA also participated in two conferences in Crete: on 8 April (in Ierapetra) and on 9 April (in Heraklion), which were organised by local	local greenhouse growers-end users, agrifood companies, farming industry,

<p>agricultural organisations, about the EU’s new common agricultural policy and current innovation programs funded by the EU. The AUA presentations were aimed at promoting the objectives of ECONUTRI, disseminating the use of the DSS NUTRISENSE by local greenhouse growers and registering local organisations and actors in the stakeholder group of the project.</p>	<p>scientific community, Local and Regional Authorities</p>
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2. UTH (P3) organized the following activities:

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
<p>Submitted an abstract to the GreenSys2023: International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems entitled “Drainage management in a cascade hydroponic system: Combination of cucumber and melon crops”. https://www.actahort.org/members/symposiaa?action=abstractforcoauthor&abstractforcoauthorlink=zKXtwXmtwXm-1968085-twXmKoXMbzKX</p>	<p>Scientific community</p>
<p>Press releases at the UTH official site and the site of the Department of Agriculture Crop Production and Rural Environment https://www.uth.gr/news/panepistimio-thessalias-symmetehei-sto-ergo-h2020-econutri</p>	<p>UTH website viewers, Farming Industry, Agrofood companies, Scientific community, Investors, authorities</p>
<p>Presentation of ECONUTRI UTH activities in more than 150 students (primary, secondary, high school and university students) that visited the Pilot Greenhouse Park of the University of Thessaly.</p>	<p>Students</p>

3. IGZ (P4) organized the following events:

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
<p>An exhibition “Internationale Grüne Woche Berlin” in Berlin, Germany on 19-29 Jan. 2023</p>	<p>Farming Industry, Scientific community, general public</p>
<p>An exhibition “International Plant Messe” (IPM) in Eseen, Germany on 24-27 Jan. 2023</p>	<p>Farming Industry, Scientific community, general public</p>
<p>Participated in the commercial fair Berlin Green Week on Jan 2023, https://www.gruenewoche.de/</p>	<p>Farming Industry, Scientific community, general public</p>
<p>Participated in the commercial fair IPM-Essen on Jan. 2023, https://www.ipmessen.de/world-trade-fair/</p>	<p>Farming Industry, Scientific community, general public</p>

4. WUR (P6)

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
<p>Attended the Xth International Symposium on Irrigation in Horticultural Crops, 29 Jan. - 2 Feb. 2023. https://ishsirrigationsa2023.com/</p>	<p>Scientific community</p>

5. NIBIO (P7)

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
Showcased ECONUTRI at the NIBIO conference on 22 Nov 2022, in the context of EU-China research collaborations	Scientific community

6. UTAD (P11)

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
attended the 5th Iberian Meeting on Pastures and Forages, 17-20 April 2023. https://www.pastos2023.com/inscripciones-reunion-iberica-pastos-forrajes/	Scientific community

7. LGNL (20) organized the following activities:

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
An online meeting on grower's soil bound crops on 19 Jan. 2023	Farming Industry
An online a meeting with organic growers on 8 Feb. 2023.	Farming Industry
A workshop "Future proof cultivation for soil crop" in De Kwakel, Netherlands on 23 Nov. 2022, where 50 soil growers participated.	Farming Industry
Published an article on the Implementation of ECONUTRI, on 9 Feb. 2023 on their website, to make the growers aware of the beginning of the project in The Netherlands.	Farming Industry, agrifood companies

8. EV ILVO (P21) organized the following events:

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
Participated in a fair "Agri Flanders" in Ghent, Belgium on 12 Jan. 2023	Farming Industry, agrifood companies, Local Authorities, General Public
A training seminar about "Ammonia-reducing measures: What's in the pipeline? Is there any news from the scientific research?" in Melle, Belgium on 19 Jan. 2023	Farming Industry, Scientific community
A conference, Vemis seminar, about emissions in Melle, Belgium on 24 March 2023 https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/nl/agenda/vemis-studiedag-vlaams-emissieonderzoek-in-de-kijker	Scientific community, Authorities
Communication campaign in EV ILVO newsletter on 3 March 2023 https://email.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/t/t-e-fdihkkk-whyurkkhd-yu/	Farming Industry, agrifood companies, Local Authorities, General public

9. JHI (P30) highlighted its experimental platform, and intercropping work

Dissemination Activity	Target Groups
At the PLEN (Plant and Environment) PhD Student Annual Conference on 'Science & Industry', held at The Royal Danish Academy of Sciences and	Scientific community

Letters, Copenhagen University, 3 Nov. 2022.	
At the "Next Generation Dairying Workshop" of the Hannah Dairy Research Foundation, held at the Moredun Research Institute, Edinburgh, 21-22 Nov. 2022. https://www.journalofdairyresearch.org/next-generation-dairying-2022.html	Farming Industry, Scientific community

5.2 Dissemination Actions in the future

To promote project participation through ECONUTRI communication channels, CETRI has asked partners to inform both AUA and itself about any new events they will be participating in at least one week before the event. Following the event, partners are asked to utilize the 'ECONUTRI D&C reporting template' (See Annex 2) to monitor progress. The participating partner fills out the document and sends it back to both AUA and CETRI. For saving time in the gathering process, it is also available in the ECONUTRI repository, the One drive, accessible to all European countries but not to the Chinese partners.

As the project progresses, partners will plan and schedule activities/events in which they intend to participate and disseminate the project results. All partners are asked to fill out the 'ECONUTRI D&C reporting for future activities template' in order to have a more efficient dissemination plan. A preliminary list of planned events is outlined in section 5.2.1 in Table 3.

5.2.1 Events planned for the years 2023/2024

The conferences and the webinars/workshops planned for the next 12 months are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3 - Events Planned (M6-18)

Partner	Date	Name of Event and link
AUA – P1 & ARI – P8	6-7 June 2023	Training seminar for growers and agronomists on “Ecologically sustainable nutrient management and fertilization of horticultural crops” as an EU Green Week Partner Event
AUA – P1	9-15 June 2023	ISHS - I International Symposium on Growing Media, Compost Utilization and Substrate Analysis for Soilless Cultivation – presentation (https://www.re3-quebec.org/en)
	26-28 June 2023	ISHS - HORCHIMODEL 2023 symposium to be held in Almeria, Spain – presentation http://www2.ual.es/horchimodel2021
	5-9 September 2023	ISHS - IX South – Eastern Europe Symposium on Vegetables and Potatoes, Bucharest – two presentations (https://symp.2023-vegetpota.asas.ro/invitation/)
	22-27 October 2023	ISHS - IV th International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems - presentation http://www.greensys2021.org/
	29-31 October 2023	31 st Scientific Congress of the Hellenic Society for Horticultural Science, organised in Heraklion, Crete - presentation
	16-19 January 2024	3rd International Workshop on Vertical Farming (VertiFarm2024) – presentation https://site.unibo.it/vertifarm2024/en
	23-27 September 2024	ISHS - I International Symposium on Protected Cultivation, Nettings and Screens for Mild Climates (https://www.ishs.org/symposium/600) - Organised by the coordinator of ECONUTRI (AUA)
UAL -P2	26-28 June 2023	HORCHIMODEL 2023 symposium to be held in Almeria, Spain - two presentations http://www2.ual.es/horchimodel2021

	22 October 2023	IVth International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems -presentation on the use of the VegSyst-DSS http://www.greensys2023.org/
UTH - P3	May or June 2023	Organisation of an Open Day to the public
	September 2023	Joint event with PestNu Green-Deal project at UTH facilities in Volos-Greece
	22 October 2023	GreenSys2023: International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems, Cancún, México, presentation, https://www.greensys2023.org/

IGZ-P4	26 -28 June 2023	ISHS HORCHIMODEL 2023 in Almeria, Spain http://www2.ual.es/horchimodel2021
	22 October 2023	International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems, Cancún, México, presentation, https://www.greensys2023.org/
	January 2024	Participation in commercial fair IPM-Essen in 2024, 2025, 2026 https://www.ipm-essen.de/world-trade-fair/
WUR-P6	22 October 2023	IVth International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems, Cancún, México, presentation/poster on the topic of DSS for irrigation in greenhouse crops http://www.greensys2023.org/
LGNL /WUR P20/P6	May 2023 June 2023 October 2023	Workshop for bio-growers Workshop for advisors Workshop for summer flowers All workshops taking place in Netherlands
NIBIO-P7	August 2023	Field day for farmers, presentation at NIBIO Særheim
	November 2024	Presentation at the NIBIO conference
ATB-P16	April 23 2023	Annual meeting of the Task Force on Emission Inventories and Projections (TFEIP) - Presentation https://www.tfeip-secretariat.org/oxford-2023
	May 2023	Annual meeting of the Task Force on Reactive Nitrogen (TFRN)-Speaker, in Dessau, Germany
	12 Sept 2023	18 th International RAMIRAN Conference-Speaker in Cambridge, UK (https://ramiran2023.org/)
EV ILVO-P21	6 June 2023	Training, TEF-event in ILVO Merelbeke
	27-28 June 2023	Organization of Workshop, Visit from ACTA, in ILVO Merelbeke
HAAS-P23	June 5-7 2023	Organization of Workshop NIBIO-HAAS Conference 2023 Harbin, China
NAU/CAU/HAAS P26/P27/P23	May 2023	Organization of Workshop Discussion on the progress of subtasks regarding biofertilisers development, in Nanjing, China
NAU/CAU/HAAS	November 2023	Training / Seminar Discussion on the progress of subtasks regarding composting in Nanjing, China
SVG/CAU P25/P27	November 2023	1) Organization of Conference in Shouguang, Shandong, China "China National Vegetable Quality Standards Summit Forum" 2) Exhibition "China Shouguang International Vegetable Seed Industry Expo"

Below are some of the activities planned to be implemented by ECONUTRI partners during the project life (See also Table 3)

By AUA-Coordinator- Laboratory of Vegetable Crops

- Six in-situ training activities for growers and agronomists on sustainable nutrient management in agriculture and the use of the DSS NUTRISense developed by AUA to support sustainable fertilization practices
- One summer school in the Summer of 2025
- Two stakeholder conferences, one in September 2024 and one in 2025
- One hackathon in 2025 to fine-tune nutrient management plans and promote the application of DSS by growers and advisors
- Visits to farmers for in-situ training on the use of the DSS developed by the AUA team of ECONUTRI
- Creation of demonstration videos
- Electronic and printed leaflets about the DSS and technologies developed by AUA to support smart nutrient management plans and optimize recycling of the fertigation effluents.
- Radio interviews in local radio stations in regions with extensive vegetable production
- At least three scientific papers in peer-reviewed international scientific journals

By AUA- Laboratory of Viticulture

- Organize a dissemination event (conference or workshop) and planning to publish an article

By AUA- Smart Farming Technology Group

- Field demonstrations measuring Vegetation Indexes (VIs) with AUA's Drones & Augmenta's Smart Tractor-Mounted Camera.
- Field Demonstrations of precision slurry application with the control system that will be developed by AUA.
- Present the results from the experimental fields to related and linked to ECONUTRI projects such as ICAERUS & SmartBiC.
- Social Media promotion through the pages of SFTG.
- Regular dissemination efforts such as presentations in potential conferences, fairs and project meetings.

By UTH (P3)

- Radio interviews in local radio stations in regions with extensive vegetable production.
- At least one article publication to local agricultural magazines.
- At least one scientific paper in peer-reviewed international scientific journals.
- High school students, BSc, and MSc student visits as part of a training activity session to get familiar with all technologies used under the frame of the project.

By IGZ (P4)

- Planning to submit a minimum of four scientific peer-reviewed articles within the time frame of the project.
- Annual participation on international commercial fairs in Germany IPM and Green Week as exhibitor.
- Press-release in Germany.

By WUR (P6)

- Articles:
 - 1) In the magazine (Dutch) 'Onder glas' (Horticulture) about improved irrigation to achieve the zero liquid discharge goals.

2) In the magazine: (Dutch) Groenten+Fruit (vegetables and fruits): about maximum recycling by using increased Na and Cl levels in drainage water.

By NIBIO (P7)

- Field days for farmers and horticulture, where the project and its results are presented
- Online presentation: A public project webpage for ECONUTRI presented on NIBIO's website
- Articles in two magazines for Norwegian farmers: "Bondevennen" and "Norsk landbruk":
 - 1) On recycling of nutrients in animal manure (methodologies) and
 - 2) On planning of fertilizing with new organic fertilizers based on waste components

By UTAD (P11)

- Organization of two seminars with growers and advisers to present and demonstrate the results:
 - 1) *Maize intercropping with legumes for forage quality improvement (September 2024 or 2025, with an open day at a demonstration field)*
 - 2) Slurry liquid fraction treatment technologies for ammonia and GHG emission reduction and better crop nutrient recovery (2024)
- Testing new composting solutions at commercial level - Transfer of knowledge on composting technologies to the stakeholder SIRO (commercial composting and plant substrates company, <https://portal.siro.pt/us/programs/cindex.aspx>).
- Field activity: From monoculture to consociations/intercropping: the added value for biodiversity: with this field activity, we aim showing the importance of intercropping as an added-value to halt biodiversity lost in European agriculture. Ecological indicators will be used to tackle this issue. Proposed date Spring 2025.

By COEXPHAL(P12)

As an association of grower organizations, COEXPHAL will mostly take care of spreading the knowledge among the end-users of the ECONUTRI technology developed, namely field advisors and growers in Almería. The University of Almería (UAL) (P2) and COEXPHAL will closely collaborate in scientific dissemination. COEXPHAL will also organize:

- **Articles.** Publish in printed monthly magazine ('AenVerde'), that directly reaches 2,500 growers in Almería and is freely available in all cooperatives. A first article will be written when the work in the greenhouses starts, explaining the objectives and expected results. A minimum of 3 articles will be published.
- **Field demonstrations.** Once the first results have been reached, i.e., after the first crop cycle in which the proposed methods have been tested and evaluated, we will organise demonstrations in the greenhouses for growers and field technicians of the cooperatives where the practical work takes place. We expect to do this in at least 4 occasions.
- **Study days.** COEXPHAL will organize a large number of study days and seminars every year, directed to either the general public or to the growers and field advisors of one of the associated companies. The findings of ECONUTRI will be presented in at least three of these events.
- **Social media.** COEXPHAL has a wide network of followers in the social media (facebook, twitter), as well as a continuous presence through the on-line version of 'AenVerde'. This allows the spread of short videos, such as recorded experiences of growers and investigators or technical instructions.

By LGNL (P20)

In cooperation with partner **WUR (P6)** a number of dissemination & communication activities are lined up.

- A page/dashboard on the website www.glastuinbouwwaterproof.nl (the greenhouse horticulture waterproof website)
- Videos/articles with growers (who work with the virtual lysimeter)
- Online presentation/video with explanation (how the virtual lysimeter works)

- A demo model (so one can try it out and see how it could benefit their company)
- Organization of events and smaller meetings with growers and advisers to present and demonstrate the results

By EV ILVO (P21)

- Planning dissemination events on Agriculture Day 17 Sept. 2023

5.2.2 Stakeholder engagement events

- Two stakeholder conferences. The first stakeholder conference will take place in Athens, in September 2024 as a satellite event in the I International Symposium of the ISHS on Protected Cultivation, Nettings and Screens for Mild Climates (organised by AUA with D. Savvas and Th. Bartzanas as conveners)

Stakeholder engagement: ECONUTRI will engage with a wide range of stakeholders throughout the project, including industry representatives, policy makers, and NGOs, to ensure that its research is relevant and useful to those who will be affected by its outcomes. ECONUTRI will organise centrally a registration platform for the core stakeholders in its webpage, where they can register upon our suggestion (invitation) and fill in a Letter of Intent. This platform is planned to act as a stakeholder forum to exchange information and transfer knowledge and experience. Knowledge and experience transfer can be bilateral i.e., from partners to stakeholders (mainly knowledge) and from stakeholders to partners (mainly practical experiences).

5.2.3 Clustering activities & EU-China Cooperation <https://china.enrichcentres.eu/>

The clustering activities and the EU-China Cooperation will be coordinated by SPI, leader of Task 1.4 in WP1. ECONUTRI will **cluster** with other funded projects under HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-03, and other relevant H2020 / Horizon Europe projects. This will create a community for knowledge and dealing with practices towards a global transition to sustainable farming systems. Engaged actors will learn more about each other, will find common issues, will share good practices and digital innovations, and will explore possibilities for future collaboration and knowledge exchange. This networking will also contribute to formulating specific policy recommendations in nutrient management technologies.

The dissemination and exploitation plans will be reinforced through clustering activities. ECONUTRI aims to focus on identifying more clusters and projects (in addition to “Trans4num” and PestNu”) that undertake similar activities with ECONUTRI and to establish common pathways for dissemination and exploitation.

A collaboration with the “**ENRICH in China**” initiative will be established, with the aim of organising one joint webinar with Chinese agricultural companies from the “ENRICH in China” network, together with the European Partners and share knowledge on best practices in nutrients management. Additionally, the news and outcomes of the project will be promoted by the channels of “ENRICH in China” (its own network, webpage, and social media – WeChat, LinkedIn and Twitter).

- ECONUTRI will organize complementary activities between EU and Chinese actors to strengthen their scientific and commercial ties;
- Disseminate the project results to targeted stakeholders in EU and China to create a knowledge ecosystem. Involved actors will exchange experiences, best practices, plus identify and co-develop innovative nutrient management approaches;

- “ENRICH in China” series webinars as a training session or clustering activities to share knowledge and increase visibility of ECONUTRI.

6 COMMUNICATION PLAN

The communication plan’s main objective is to include activities and tools that will raise awareness about the project, its main goal and objectives to multiple audiences beyond the project’s own community, informing and reaching out to society and showing the importance of new nutrient management technologies leading to reduced environmental footprints. The communication plan includes the visual identity of the project, the website, the leaflet, the roll up banner and the social media profiles. Furthermore, future communication actions are also displayed.

6.1 Visual Identity

The communication tools are the project’s visual identity. They have been developed in the first four months of the project and will be used for the ECONUTRI project and furthermore for the network that will be established during the project’s lifetime and beyond. All the tools have been designed by WP1 leader CETRI. The ECONUTRI visual identity consists of:

- ECONUTRI Logo and colour guide
- ECONUTRI Deliverable template
- ECONUTRI Presentation template
- ECONUTRI Agenda template
- ECONUTRI Minutes template

6.1.1 ECONUTRI Logo

After the kick-off meeting, CETRI distributed the logo to the whole consortium and various file formats for different uses (website, leaflet, social channels), were uploaded in the One drive repository folder. This unique logo is the primary representation of the project and expresses its distinct visual character. (Figure 1)

Figure 1 - ECONUTRI logo

Furthermore, for Horizon Europe projects, all communication forms shall have the EU logo and the funding statement (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - EU logo

6.1.2 ECONUTRI colours

The ECONUTRI colour schemes shown in Figure 3 are the two colours used in the logo and can be utilized throughout the project materials to organize and emphasize various sections of content. These colours will also influence the colour scheme of all other communication materials (templates, leaflets, rollout banner, social media platforms, articles)

Figure 3- *ECONUTRI logo colours*

6.1.3 ECONUTRI Templates

CETRI, AUA and METEC have created a number of ECONUTRI templates in order to maintain consistency in the layout and appearance of all project uses. All the templates feature the project logo, the EU logo, and the ECONUTRI colours. In order to utilize the templates as effective communication tools, all partners have been instructed to use the correct templates for their intended purposes. The templates that have been developed so far are:

- **ECONUTRI Deliverable template** to ensure that all project Deliverables will have consistent format. The font and colours used in the text will match those used in the ECONUTRI logo creating consistent visual identity of the project. Also, all Public Deliverables will be uploaded on the website so interested stakeholders can easily access and download them. This can promote transparency, and knowledge sharing, which are important values in European projects.
- **ECONUTRI Presentation template** to ensure consistency in the overall look of the presentations while still allowing partners to add their own content and tailor their presentations to their specific needs and audiences.
- **ECONUTRI Agenda template** to support the consortium in the organization of events. An agenda can provide potential attendees with a clear idea of what will be covered during the event, the timing of different sessions, and who will be speaking or presenting. Making the agenda available online can also make it easier to share and promote the event through social media channels, email, or newsletters. This can help increase the visibility of the event and reach a wider audience.
- **ECONUTRI Minutes template** to help keep track of what was discussed and decided. It can also help partners who were absent to stay informed. Sharing the notes with everyone involved in the project can ensure that all partners are on the same page and can contribute to achieving the project's goals.

6.2 Website

In today’s digital world the website serves as the primary dissemination and communication tool. The ECONUTRI website www.econutri-project.eu/ has been launched since the beginning of the project by CETRI. The website structure and design are presented below in Table 4.

Table 4 – ECONUTRI Website structure

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Home	Project	Outputs	Communication & Dissemination	Newsletter	Stakeholder Engagement	News
	Objective	Public Abstracts	Publications		Demonstration sites	
	Structure	Public Deliverables	Conferences		Clustering activities	
	Partners		Videos		Workshops	
			Gallery			
			Promotional Material			

As the project develops, the website will undergo frequent updates with continuous contribution from the partners. The latest developments will be shared through newsletters, press releases, research outputs, and deliverables, all available on the project website. These updates aim to generate interest and engage with diverse sectors of society.

The website contains links to the social media account platforms on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. All public deliverables generated for the project will be accessible to all visitors and easy to download.

To track the impact of the website through the number of visitors, **google analytics** has been enabled and will be monitored continuously. The ECONUTRI webpage is displayed as screenshot in Annex 1.

6.3 Leaflet

CETRI has produced an ECONUTRI leaflet to be distributed at conferences and other relevant events related to nutrient management in agriculture, across EU countries and China.

The project leaflet is a key communication component and will accompany project partners at all communication-related activities. It will serve as the first outreach document of the project that provides an insight into the core objectives, the challenges, the concept, partners, and EU funding programme.

The leaflet is distributed in digital format to all partners, who are responsible for printing it at their own cost and utilizing it at appropriate events.

The leaflet is threefold and it includes: 1) project logo, title and website, 2) partners logos, 3) project information, 4) social media platforms, 5) the challenge, 6) the solution and 7) who benefits

Figure 5 - ECONUTRI rollup banner

6.5 Social media

Social media is a vital tool in the 21st century that amplifies messages, reaching a wider audience, and allows for interaction through informal communication. So, it is important to develop a social media strategy to promote the ECONUTRI project effectively.

Posts will be designed to encourage people to like or follow the ECONUTRI pages and to increase the awareness and interest on the development of the project.

Visual content, such as images and videos, can be more engaging and memorable than text-based content and can help tell the story of ECONUTRI. Followers will be encouraged to share their own content related to ECONUTRI in their websites and personal channels.

An increased engagement with the target audience will be to respond/react to comments, messages and mentions on ECONUTRI social media channels, thus building a stronger relationship. By using social media channels, communication becomes more direct and personal than many other forms of communication (newspaper, radio, television).

To identify which aspects of the strategy are effective and reaching out to the audience, it is necessary to monitor and measure social media profiles. The **analytics tools** provided by each platform will be used to

track engagement metrics like likes, shares, and comments. If the effectiveness is not satisfactory then different approaches will be considered.

ECONUTRI will use four different social media platforms to target different stakeholder groups: LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. The four profiles have been created, displayed in Table 5, and are also linked to the ECONUTRI website. Each of the four profiles are displayed as screenshots in Annex 3.

Table 5 - ECONUTRI Social media profiles

Social Media Profile	Profile Link	Status (up to 11 April 2023)
	Econutri-project	278 followers
	econutri_project	31 followers / 27 likes
	@Econutri30	22 followers
	econutri30	54 followers

CETRI has initiated the creation of posts, primarily related to the kick-off meeting and conference attendance. Furthermore, almost all partners have published the ECONUTRI project in their own website. The next step is to develop a campaign to introduce the consortium, followed by the work package framework.

All partners are encouraged to follow and share the above ECONUTRI social media accounts (Table 5) in order to promote the project, broaden the ECONUTRI community and ultimately reach the 1500 followers as promised in the proposal. CETRI is responsible for ensuring the profiles remain up to date and active with news and relevant posts during and after the project lifetime, with the contribution from all partners.

One of the benefits of social media is that it allows people to connect and communicate with others from all over the world, to participate in discussions on a wide range of topics and also learn and grow from the diverse perspectives and viewpoints of each other.

The use of hashtags helps in this sense and several are incorporated into ECONUTRI posts such as #fertilizers, #nutrients, #NH3emissions, #agrofood, #Chinapartners, #plantnutrition, #HorizonEurope.

It is important to note that the use of the '@' symbol will always be included when referring to the ECONUTRI project on all four social media profiles!

6.6 Communication actions in the future

Furthermore, as the project continues to advance, more communication materials will be developed to portray the research done, the new findings and any related news. Such as:

- **A poster** will soon be developed to be used in workshops or any other event the partners will attend. It can be adapted in line with the needs of specific events.
- **Videos and podcasts** with project information and interviews will be produced and uploaded in YouTube.

- **Press releases** will help to generate media coverage, which can increase the project's visibility and credibility. There will be a press release at least once a year after the annual meetings written and distributed in each partner's country.
- **ECONUTRI Innovation Handbook** will be delivered in M40 to ensure that best practices, lessons learnt, and policy recommendations are clearly and effectively understood in the agricultural community.
- **Extra promotional material** will be produced as required due to clustering activities with sister projects (i.e., leaflet, poster)
- **e-Newsletter** will be published every six months summarising all activities related to the project and targeting the research and academic community, farming industry, policymakers. CETRI in collaboration with the consortium, will gather the content for the newsletter and will also oversee its distribution. All partners are encouraged to contribute articles on latest research and news items to be included in the newsletter. Each issue of the newsletter will be made available on the website and various social media platforms to increase its reach. A subscription to the newsletter will also be possible through the ECONUTRI website. Additionally, partners and stakeholders will be prompted to share the newsletter through their own dissemination channels within their network.

All communication tools with their respective KPIs are described below in Table 6.

Table 6 – Communication tools

Communication tool	Performance indicators		
	P1	P2	Means of verification
ECONUTRI website with basic project info, objectives, news, open access articles and publishable deliverables.	100,000 websites visits; 200 downloads per public deliverable	300,000 new visits; 2000 new total downloads	Google analytics
e-Newsletter summarising all activities related to the project.	every 6 months, 600 recipients	every 6 months, 1000 new recipients	List of newsletter subscribers
Promotional material in digital and hardcopy form (posters, leaflets/flyers).	e-material sent to 1000 recipients	2000 recipients	Project reporting
Videos with project information and interviews	>10,000 YouTube views, 10 videos	>20,000 new YouTube views	YouTube analytics
Social media presence with project accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram.	>5 posts per month 1,500 followers per project account	1,500 new followers per project account	Social media analytics
Project workshops: 3 thematic workshops will be organised. Locations will be arranged subject to covid-19 situation.	200 attendees	-	Project reporting
Visits to schools: each partner will visit at least one school in its territory.	28 schools	200 schools	Project reporting

<p>Promotion through hackathons. A hackathon will be organised to fine-tune nutrient management plans and promote the application of DSS by growers and advisors.</p>	<p>100 participants</p>	<p>>1,000 followers in social media (e.g., YouTube)</p>	<p>Project reporting</p>
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7 EXPLOITATION PLAN

The exploitation strategy of ECONUTRI relates to the way each project partner individually, and the project partnership, intend to use the project results for scientific, societal, economic purposes, as well as for policy making. The strong industrial participation in ECONUTRI brings strong expertise and benefits for an effective exploitation strategy. In this framework, the consortium will identify opportunities and define appropriate **exploitable results**.

As described in the Grant Agreement, after having defined the ownership of each result, partners will explore and define their exploitation plan e.g., patenting, knowledge exploitation, royalties, and market product development. In this way, each exploitable result will be associated with a working group for identifying specific opportunities.

The goal is to create an **enabling support system** that maximises the **large-scale uptake** of the project exploitable results during and after project completion, ensuring that as many solutions as possible reach the farming industry. To achieve this, **key aspects for exploitation** will be addressed through support to project partners concerning issues related to IPR, assessment of regulations and standards in Europe that apply to the ECONUTRI solutions and develop exploitation plans for the project exploitable results.

Exploitation will be divided into 3 phases:

<p>P1</p>	<p>Phase 1 – Initial exploitation (during project implementation): Initial exploitation activities will commence with the onset of the ECONUTRI programme, coordinated by CETRI, SPI and AUA. The initial take-up activities will enable technology adaptation and integration, while ECONUTRI systems will be reviewed, optimised, and demonstrated at full scale, thereby mitigating the risk of technology roll-out to competitors. Relationship with potential customers will be established. Possible formation of a joint venture that will take the form of a new distinct legal entity or constitute a business unit within an already existing company.</p>
	<p>Phase 2 – Early-stage commercialisation and implementation at Full Scale (for 1 year market roll-out): Early exploitation activities will take place targeting take-up of the innovative systems by early customers (primarily large farmers). Investment for the advanced demonstrated systems is anticipated to be provided directly by the industrial partners. However, external investment will also be considered, if capital finance is not available within the required timeframe. Partners will also consider licensing a limited number of private agri-food companies to use novel products, to ensure the appropriate funding for full commercialisation.</p>

P2	<p>Phase 3 – Exploitation within European and Chinese Markets (starting 1 year after the project end):</p> <p>Having validated the implementation and roll-out of the technology with partners, the consortium will commence exploiting the technology across the wider European and Chinese farming markets. Accordingly, discussions that take place with European farmers will then be transformed into contracts. It is anticipated that large and medium farms across Europe will invest directly to pay for the full ECONUTRI systems and services, to benefit from the innovative approach with a fast ROI. Smaller farms will be targeted as well from the 3rd year of exploitation. 5 years after the onset of the commercialisation process, partners will consider licensing more nutrient management companies with the ECONUTRI technology, further increasing the penetration rate of the developed solutions in the market.</p>
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The WP1 leader CETRI will ensure key exploitable assets are developed with post-project sustainability in mind, and business/sustainability cases will be developed/tested throughout project activities, aiming to convert the ECONUTRI innovative technologies into marketable products.

The exploitation plan will gather all aspects related to IPR management, regulations & standards and market studies in its second version in month 18.

Additional public and private funding for further TRL development will also be screened and analyzed. IPR issues will be mainly covered by the Consortium Agreement (CA) to devise appropriate IP strategies by providing the necessary measures to protect IPR & licensing, while facilitating uptake of the ECONUTRI solutions in various scenarios.

SPI will develop a business plan (part of the PDEC in the month 18 version), defining how to commercialise the products/solutions stemming from the project, as such it will engage in a thorough market analysis, contemplating also the target customers and the competition. This analysis will involve conducting market research to identify potential customers and market opportunities. With a comprehensive understanding of the market, a marketing strategy to promote the solution or sell the products will be conducted. Overall, the business plan will serve as a roadmap for commercializing the products/solutions stemming from the project, ensuring that the team is able to achieve its goals while delivering value to customers and stakeholders.

The ultimate goal is to achieve the optimal implementation of proposed technologies and demonstrate their viability, paving the way for potential commercial exploitation. The ECONUTRI key exploitable results are listed below in Table 8.

Table 8 - ECONUTRI Key Exploitable Results and expected TRLs

	Key Exploitable Results	IPR Owner	TRL
1	Integrated ECONUTRI system to transition to circular bio-based systems in agriculture	All partners	7
2	NUTRISense: advanced version available on-line on subscription basis to optimise fertigation	AUA	8
3	Hyperspectral analysis algorithms for estimating nutrient needs	AUA	7
4	Practical System-Function Indicators for Sustainable Cropping: NUE & other ecosystem services	JHI	8
5	OTICE: advanced version available for wide on-farm use	EV ILVO & ATB	8
6	Guides to (i) nutrient recovery from organic rest products, (ii) spreading of pelleted organic fertilizers	NIBIO, UNITO	7
7	Optimised steering software of manure spreaders for optimal manure spreading & emission reduction	Vervaet/ODYC	7
8	VEGSYST-DSS: an advanced version will be freely available on-line to optimise fertigation solutions	UAL	9
9	VIRTUAL LYSIMETER: advanced DSS for optimal fertigation, on-line available on subscription basis	WUR	8
10	Nutrient supply tailored to crop needs and additives to reduce gaseous emissions in animal farms	ARI	7
11	Innovative technologies reducing GHG and NH ₃ emissions in barns, storages and on fields	WP4 partners	7
12	Protocols and standards for sustainable cascade hydroponics farming, system simulation/validation	UTH	8
13	LCA and model-based simulators of three key innovations that reduce nutrient leaching and GHGs	IGZ, AUA	7
14	Compact robust real-time 8-ion nutrient ion analyser for horticulture. Integrated with NUTRISense	CG	9
15	Dissemination of DSS for precision fertigation management using diverse diffusion approaches	UAL, COEXPHAL	8

16	Protocols on use of novel microbiological consortia to accelerate composting of organic rest products	INHORT	7
17	Integrated measures for controlling of black soil degradation and NUE improvement	HAAS	7
18	N stabilizers to enhance NUE and reduce N pollution	CAU, SVG	7
19	Humic acid-based fertilizer reducing fertilizer input and improving fertilizer efficiency	Stanley	7
20	An integrated approach to improve soil fertility and health towards crop production	NAU	7
21	Quantitative recommendation of N and P in organic cropping to reduce N and P content in profile soil	HAAFS	7

7.1 Partner specific exploitation Plans

All partners are highly interested in strengthening their organisations by exploiting the project's end results. In line with the proposal the organizations are divided into 4 groups.

- **Industrial partners** CG, CETRI, METEC, ODYC, Vervaet, WP, Augmenta, SPI, Stanley and SVG intend to grow in their dedicated fields getting benefitted by the new business opportunities the exploitation of the project innovations will create.
- **Research partners** AUA, UAL, UTH, IGZ, JHI, WUR, NIBIO, UNITO, UTAD, ATB, EV ILVO, HAAS, NAU, CAU and HAAFS will be strengthened by actions, such as promotion of their novel technologies to the private sector for commercial exploitation, joint publications, student and staff exchanges, participation in workshops and training courses, and presentation at meetings, as well as making sure that their research is applied in the most efficient way.
- **Public and non-profit partners** ARI, ESSRG, COEXPHAL and LGNL will have the opportunity to transfer generated forefront knowledge to their regions / members.

Several research partners have provided a preliminary exploitation plan in Table 9 below.

Table 9 - Partner Primary Exploitation plan

Partner Name	Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) P1
Content to be exploited	Web-accessible Decision Support System (DSS) NUTRISENSE
Approach towards Exploitation	NUTRISENSE, as a DSS supporting soilless growers is already on-line available on a subscription basis through the link https://nutrisense.online/ . The AUA team plans to further develop and optimize this DSS by adding extra versions for soil-grown crops and for soilless growers who wish to use ion selective electrodes (ISEs) to optimize nutrient recycling in closed-loop soilless cultivation systems. The upgraded NUTRISENSE will be fully commercialized as it will be offered as a full package of services for sustainable nutrient management in open-field and greenhouse vegetable crops on subscription basis by a commercial company.
Partner Name	University of Thessaly (UTH) P3
Content to be exploited	DSS for water and nutrient management simulation in a cascade cropping system
Approach towards Exploitation	The DSS will be used to simulate the water and nutrient inputs and outputs in a cascade system where the drainages of a donor crop (cucumbers) will be fully used to meet the nutritional needs of a secondary crop (melons). UTH, as a research partner, will proceed to joint publications based on the efficiency of this prediction model as well as to training courses to further exploit the obtained results
Partner Name	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO) P7
Content to be exploited	Nutrient calibration is necessary in order to valorize materials derived from biowaste processing.

Approach towards Exploitation	<p>Biowastes contain valuable nutrients, that will imply economic losses if not recovered. Moreover, if the nutrients are spread to the environment, nature values can be damaged or even destroyed. Therefore, the recovery of the nutrients and transformation of wastes into valuable products will be important for the economy and the environment.</p> <p>We aim at extracting phosphorus (struvite precipitation) and nitrogen (NH₄ – stripping) from the waste streams, for more economic and environmental sound uses. Our work will be to optimize and demonstrate these technologies on lab scale to prepare for industrialization of the processes. Enriching biowaste-based fertilizer products may be important to upgrade the fertilizers and improve their ability to compete with mineral fertilizers. The knowledge and technology developed will be disseminated/demonstrated to encourage widespread adaptation.</p>
Partner Name	Agricultural Research Institute (ARI) P8
Content to be exploited	Policy making
Approach towards Exploitation	The ECONUTRI technology will be disseminated in Cyprus, to the Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment, for policy making decisions. The results will be used for the creation of a handbook that will be distributed to the farmers.
Partner Name	Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB) P16
Content to be exploited	Urease inhibitor to reduce emissions from dairy barns. Effect of fast manure removal by using cleaning robots and manure scrapers on emissions from dairy barns.
Approach towards Exploitation	ATB will evaluate the effect of urease inhibitors and manure-cleaning robots at real scale as both of these techniques possibly reduce the emission of GHGs and NH ₃ up to 20% from dairy barns. After the successful evaluation, ATB will promote the adoption/utilization/sale of urease inhibitors and cleaning robots at large scale to increase the overall mitigation of gaseous emissions from livestock production systems.
Partner Name	Institute for Agricultural and Food Research (EV ILVO) P21
Content to be exploited	ILVO will evaluate the effect of fast manure removal in a fattening pig barn as this technique possibly reduces the emission of GHGs and NH ₃ . ILVO will also evaluate the functionality of an online emission monitoring system (OTICE) in pilot trials.
Approach towards Exploitation	After the successful evaluation, ILVO will promote the application of fast manure removal at large scale to increase the overall mitigation of gaseous emissions from livestock production systems. Furthermore, ILVO will promote the application of an online emission monitoring system at large scale, since it can contribute to very useful insights in the emissions of barns and could result in adaptation of the farmers management to reduce the gaseous emissions from their barns
Partner Name	James Hutton Institute (JHI) P30
Content to be exploited	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "Innovation Stacking" of agronomic approaches in a long-term experimental integrated platform - the Centre for Sustainable Cropping (CSC). The stacked approaches themselves are worth reporting. 2. LCA of the CSC platform (attributorial and consequential LCA). LCA impact assessment can be linked to ESs indicators. So, system function as well as impact can be evaluated. This linking of LCA to ES is also a technology development. 3. LCA data to inform development of GOBLIN -model - to generate "Crop-GOBLIN" for identification of best scenarios for upscaling of integrated farming approach.

	<p>4. Data and insights from the WP3 on "legume-legume" crop mixtures trial can:</p> <p>a) provide an informative narrative to limit synthetic fertiliser N use; and</p> <p>b) data will feed into LCA, development of crop-GOBLIN, and so assess crop-mixture based solutions in the "which cropped system/rotation" scenario analysis.</p>
Approach towards Exploitation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. collect and assess data, methods development, peer-reviewed publications necessary as evidence base. 2. in parallel with the above make initial key-data findings known to key industry stakeholders/sponsors. 3. showcase findings at key stakeholder events: Arable Scotland, Royal Highland Show, Hannah Dairy Research Foundation (annual meeting), international research conferences (International Legume Society). 4. LCA approach, and crop-GOBLIN model made openly available and Open Access resource. 5. build integrated farm network around the CSC platform.

It should be noted here that NUTRISENSE in its two versions (SOIL NUTRISENSE, SOILLESS NUTRISENSE) is the only commercially exploitable result produced by the project, specifically by AUA. However, other partners are working on more commercially exploitable results which are still in progress. The progress with the commercially exploitable results by other partners will be described in detail in the deliverable D1.2 due in month 18.

Furthermore, AUA will be a beneficiary for the DSS NUTRISENSE. The beneficiaries of DSS created by other partners for ECONUTRI (e.g. the VegSys by UAL and the Virtual Lysimeter by WUR) will be the respective partners who have created these DSS.

The intellectual Property Rights of NUTRISENSE belong solely to AUA, as AUA is the sole creator of this DSS. However, other partners and specifically WONDERPLANT and ARI are also using NUTRISENSE free of charge during the project life and thus they also benefit from this DSS. Furthermore, a substantial number of stakeholders (>10) are currently benefiting from NUTRISENSE as they make use of this DSS free of charge in pilot studies and tests.

8 CONCLUSION

The deliverable D1.1 - Plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication, is a strategic document that defines the planning and scheduling of the different activities to be implemented in the frame of dissemination and communication. The aim of this deliverable is to setup an initial plan at an early stage of the project in order to coordinate in an efficient way the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities that have been agreed in the Grant Agreement of ECONUTRI.

The ECONUTRI Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy aims to increase awareness of the project's innovative nature and optimize its influence by disseminating its results to stakeholders and the general public using suitable means and methods. Consequently, the PDEC offers partners direction on how to design and implement their dissemination efforts and serves as a tool for the consortium to monitor and oversee the advancement of ECONUTRI.

In M18, the PDEC will be updated as necessary to align with the project's progress and will include more comprehensive information on the partners' exploitation strategies.

ECONUTRI partners will be accountable for communicating project outcomes via ECONUTRI social media platforms and their individual networks, while AUA and CETRI will oversee the utilization of online tools and channels to ensure broad exposure at the highest level.

ANNEX 3

ECONUTRI LinkedIn profile

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn profile for 'econutri'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with icons for Home, My Network, Jobs, and Messaging. Below this is a blue banner that reads 'You are viewing this page as a member'. The profile header features a green background with a plant growing from soil, surrounded by icons representing water, sun, and nutrients. The Econutri logo is on the left, and a 'Funded by the European Union' badge is on the right. The profile name is 'Econutri-Project', with a description: 'Innovative technologies for ECOlogically sustainable NUTRient management in agriculture. Grant Agreement no 101081858'. Below the description, it lists industries: 'Agriculture, Construction, Mining Machinery Manufacturing' and location: 'Athens', with '278 followers'. There are three buttons: 'Following', 'Visit website', and 'More'. At the bottom, there is a navigation menu with 'Home', 'About', 'Posts', 'Jobs', 'People', and 'Videos'.

ECONUTRI Facebook account

The screenshot shows the Facebook profile for 'econutri_project'. The cover photo is a green background with a plant growing from soil, surrounded by icons representing water, sun, and nutrients. The profile picture is the Econutri logo. The name is 'econutri_project' and the bio is '27 "Μου αρέσει!" • 31 ακόλουθοι'. There are three buttons: 'Πρωήθηση', 'Διαχείριση', and 'Επεξεργασία'. At the bottom right, there is a badge that reads 'Επεξεργασία φωτογραφίας εξωφύλλου' and 'the European Union'.

ECONUTRI Twitter account

ECONUTRI Instagram account

econutri30

Επεξεργασία προφίλ

8 δημοσιεύσεις

54 ακόλουθοι

Ακολουθείτε 2 χρήστες

Econutri Project

Innovative technologies for Ecologically sustainable Nutrient management in agriculture aiming to eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air.

ΔΗΜΟΣΙΕΥΣΕΙΣ

ΑΠΟΘΗΚΕΥΜΕΝΑ

ΜΕ ΕΤΙΚΕΤΑ

***eco*nutri**

<https://econutri-project.eu/>

